

MORFEO LOR: a VR-based maintenance approach

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ABSTRACT

The Extremely Large Telescope (ELT), currently under construction by ESO on Cerro Armazones in Chile, will be the world's largest optical/near-infrared telescope. Among its first-light instruments, MORFEO (Multiconjugate adaptive Optics Relay for ELT Observations) represents one of the most complex adaptive optics modules ever designed, feeding the MICADO camera with corrected wide-field images and HARMONY. Given the extraordinary complexity of the instrument and the challenging operational environment of the ELT, maintenance operations must be carefully planned, validated, and optimized long before the telescope sees first light. This work presents a Virtual Reality (VR) framework developed to simulate, test, and refine maintenance procedures for the MORFEO LOR (Laser-Oriented Relay) subsystem. By immersing operators in a high-fidelity digital twin of the instrument, the framework enables the collection of both qualitative and quantitative ergonomic data, the identification of optimal access strategies, and the generation of detailed maintenance documentation all prior to any physical intervention. The integration of a Large Language Model (LLM) further enhances the workflow by automating report generation and stress-testing procedures through large-scale virtual simulations. One of the first application of the VR on the astronomical instrumentation consist of investigate one maintenance applied on the Natural Guide Star (NGS) subsystem of MORFEO operation both in a quantitative and qualitative ways exploiting the big advantage that the VR can offer in this and many other applications.

Keywords: Virtual Reality, VR, MORFEO, LOR, FREDA, Natural Guide Star

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 The ELT and its instrumentation challenge and the advantages with the Virtual Reality

The ELT, with its 39-metre segmented primary mirror, represents a generational leap in ground-based astronomy. Its unprecedented light-collecting area will enable observations of exoplanet atmospheres, the first galaxies, and the large-scale structure of the Universe at sensitivities never achieved. However, the sheer scale and complexity of the ELT introduce equally unprecedented challenges in instrument engineering, integration, and maintenance.

Figure 1 ELT overview with instrumentation, ESO credits.

Figure 1 depicts the size and number of subsystems involved on the Nasmyth platform, where the instrument are located; among the various instruments to be installed is the first-generation MORFEO. Such complexity requires iterative and meticulous design, as well as the definition of detailed maintenance operations. The feasibility of these operations is often hard to assess in advance. Applying Virtual Reality (VR) to these procedures can significantly optimize both the design and operational lifetime of the instruments in several ways:

- During the design, the possibility to investigate the feasibility of the procedure, alignment procedure, accessibility and ergonomics.
- During the review phase it is possible to examine the procedure using guided and full immersive experience, tracking comments and notes, pointing out criticalities and taking actions.
- Extract quantitative data teach procedure to the external partners and technician.

1.2 What is MORFEO?

MORFEO (Mult conjugate adaptive Optics Relay For ELT Observations) is the adaptive optics (AO) module designed to feed the MICADO imager (i.e., ELT's first light near-infrared camera) with wide-field, diffraction-limited images. MORFEO implements a Mult conjugate Adaptive Optics (MCAO) strategy, which corrects for atmospheric turbulence across a relatively wide field of view by using multiple deformable mirrors conjugated to different altitudes in the atmosphere.

MORFEO uses a constellation of Laser Guide Stars (LGS) to probe the turbulent layers of the atmosphere, combined with Natural Guide Stars (NGS) for low-order correction and tip-tilt sensing. The system comprises several key subcomponents, most of which are directly embedded in the main MORFEO body (in the background in Figure 2), with the remaining instrumentation located inside the MICADO volume (in the forefront in Figure 2). As shown in Figures Figure 1 and Figure 2, MORFEO spans an impressive 8 x 7 x 5 m. This massive scale makes it an ideal initial case study for integrating VR across the project's phases.

Figure 2 MICADO in front and MORFEO in the back.

1.3 What is the LOR?

The LOR is a critical opto-mechanical subsystem of MORFEO. the purpose of the subsystem is to correct the low order aberration of the atmosphere looking at three natural stars in the sky. the opto-mechanics on the board are described better in [1], but a brief introduction of the size of the device is needed to get the complexity of the operation. What is reported in Figure 3 is the LOR volume and its design. The volume has a diameter of almost 4 meters located at 4 m high from the ground. The described structure is located in between the SCAO bench and the MICADO vacuum vessel. When everything is mounted at the Telescope the LOR is accessible only radially using the scaffolding that embrace the MICADO structure.

Figure 3 LOR subsystem in the design volume

The LOR bench hosts sensitive optical and detector components, including the FREDA camera, and is physically enclosed between the MICADO cover and the SCAO bench. This location, while optically optimal, makes the LOR one of the most access-constrained subsystems in the entire instrument stack. Any maintenance intervention on the LOR replacing optical components, realigning detectors, or servicing the FREDA camera must be performed in a spatially confined volume, potentially at significant height within the telescope structure, without disturbing the surrounding instruments.

This is why VR-based planning of LOR maintenance is essential. The procedure presented in this study is just one example of many procedures that could be implemented. The procedure involves several aspects, standards and tasks that have been structured into a sequence of subsequent steps:

- **Pre-entry checks**
 - Ensure all Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) is correctly worn
 - Verify that all required tools and basic cleaning equipment are available
 - Confirm that two operators are present (mandatory for safety: the second operator must be able to initiate first aid and call for help in case of an accident)
 - Ensure the facility maintains an aseptic environment before entry
- **Facility access & interlock activation**
 - Open the access gate to enter the facility
 - Verify that the Interlock system has activated, preventing any internal movement of the LOR module
 - Communicate with the outside handler to confirm the interlock is functioning properly
- **Access to the FREDA camera**
 - Proceed to the second floor, second section on the left
 - Remove the access panel and position it so that it does not impede operations

- Disconnect the railing directly in front of the removed panel
- Contact the crane operator to position the additional platform, allowing the worker to reach the cameras without stepping on internal LOR components
- Once the platform is in place, fasten it and attach the support plate to enable access to the back of the FREDA camera
- **Pump connection & re-pumping**
 - Verify that the turbomolecular pump has been pre-positioned near the work area
 - Connect the pump to the FREDA camera following the prescribed instructions
 - Initiate the re-pumping operation fulfilling the time needed for the repumping.
 - The operator may leave the site during this phase and return upon completion
- **Post-pumping checks & pump removal**
 - Verify that the pump and camera are properly decoupled
 - Inspect the LOR module's operating area and ensure no contamination or dirt has been left
 - Secure the pump to the crane unit and have it removed from the structure (manual carrying is not permitted due to weight)
- **Restoration & exit**
 - Remove the platform from the work area
 - Re-fasten the railing in its original position
 - Reposition and screw down the access panel
 - Perform a final cleanliness check of the site
 - Exit the structure and ensure the access gate is closed — failure to do so will prevent proper operation of the interlock safety system

**Figure 4 Depiction of the LOR and the MICADO vessel removing the SCAO visibility.
Black panels are used for the inspection of the LOR**

2. METHODOLOGY

This section presents methodology adopted to implement the real maintenance procedure in the virtual environment. The objective was not only to recreate the actual layout of the system, but also to simulate and verify a series of real work operations. By integrating core steps into the VR application, it was possible to examine the workflow, accessibility, and usability aspects directly inside the simulation, providing useful indications for both design improvement and operator training.

2.1 From CAD to mesh: the 3D model pipeline

The very first step was to build an efficient pipeline for converting CAD files into game engine-compatible formats. This process was essential to guarantee that models could be optimized and implemented in the environment without compromising performance or structural precision.

The CAD files were provided in STEP format, which is widely supported across a variety of engineering tools. Unfortunately, this format is not natively supported in the Unity game engine, making it necessary to establish a conversion workflow.

Taking advantage of the interoperability within the Autodesk software suite, the transition from a mechanical CAD pipeline to an architectural visualization pipeline was straightforward. This compatibility enabled the direct conversion of the original mechanical model into the FBX format, which is commonly supported by architectural software due to its built-in rendering capabilities. FBX is a widely supported format across both rendering and game development pipelines. Despite having different requirements and constraints, both rendering and gaming industries rely on similar techniques for 3D modelling visualization, and often share common file standards. Rendering software typically uses detailed, high-polygon models to achieve photorealism, while game engines require optimized, low-polygon geometry for real-time performance. Once the conversion from CAD to a rasterized model was completed, the model had to be optimized to meet the requirements of real-time rendering. This task was accomplished using Blender, a modelling tool particularly suited for preparing assets for game engines and represented a core step in guaranteeing smooth performance and proper interaction within the virtual environment. After completing this process, the models could be effectively used in Unity.

Even though a high level of details can improve realism, a compromise between resolution and practicality must be found. For industrial applications, a one-to-one replica is often not necessary, as a simplified version maintains spatial fidelity and functional representation while improving simulation performance. For this reason, elements involved in the procedure were optimized without excessively altering their appearance, while non-functional elements were either removed or simplified. Small details carry a computational cost which, if left unmanaged, could cause performance issues in large-scale applications. The most important area of the scene is undoubtedly the interior of the LOR module, where the most delicate components of MORFEO are housed; a high level of geometric fidelity was therefore maintained in this region. Outside this zone, only features visible to the naked eye were preserved, and polygon reduction was applied to more distant elements as standard practice. This allowed for immersive visuals without placing excessive demands on hardware.

Regarding coloring of the 3D model, to facilitate the identification of key components that may require repositioning, the color coding utilized during the CAD design phase was maintained and applied also to the rasterized model, as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 5 Overviews of the scene built in the Unity environment

Furthermore, maintaining the colour scheme from the CAD phase proved valuable both for testing and training purposes. First, visual consistency made it considerably easier to discuss potential layout improvements. Second, it facilitated components recognition and spatial awareness. Of course, the physical components will not feature such vivid and well-defined colours; therefore, showcasing their location clearly essential in the training phase to achieve accurate and safe maintenance.

2.2 From real to virtual: the maintenance procedure

To achieve a meaningful experience, it is not necessary to perform every action exactly as it would be done. The most important aspect is the relevance of the actions performed, as explained in [2]; realism does not always coincide with relevance. For this reason, starting from the actual maintenance procedure, a preliminary stage of task subdivision was performed, in order to identify the most relevant operations that were required to be replicated in the VR environment, this consisted in chunking the procedure into small subsequent steps, as suggested in **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata..**

The second key aspect to consider for a successful implementation is the cognitive effort induced by the application. It is crucial for a simulation to account for the user's cognitive effort as it largely influences both the perception of the experience and its outcome. For instance, an overly demanding application might impair the potential benefits of VR and may even trigger adverse reactions such as nausea or dizziness, as suggested by [4]. On the other hand, a poorly designed training application might result in low levels of cognitive engagement, that might lead to low learning outcomes [5]. The procedure considered for the current application is highly detailed, as one would expect from a technical manual; however, such granularity is excessive for an application of this type.

Therefore, it is important to minimise the components of cognitive load that are not beneficial to user's cognitive engagement. To do so, we limited tedious actions that did not contribute meaningful definition of the procedure, all while not impacting the significance, nor the interactivity of the application, which has a paramount role when addressing the cognitive load [6]. At the end of this process, the six most relevant steps were identified, ensuring a procedure that retains all the essential aspects of the real one without placing undue strain on the user's cognitive resources. A simplified version of the procedure steps is depicted in **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata..**

Figure 6 Core steps of the procedure, that ensure a good relevance for the application

Once the key elements were identified, it was necessary to determine the level of realism required for the interactions themselves. Repeating the same action multiple times is unnecessary and counterproductive; therefore, all actions that would otherwise be repeated to complete a task were reduced to a single interaction, preserving the correct progression

of the procedure without making it overly complicated. To illustrate this with an example: removing the panel requires acting on the four fastening blocks located at its corners. Rather than requiring the user to interact with each one individually, once the first block is removed the remaining three follow automatically, allowing the operator to remove the panel immediately.

A further important aspect concerns user guidance. Instructions must be communicated to the user in a clear and timely manner to ensure proper learning of the procedure, which is particularly relevant during the training phase of the application. As discussed in [7], effective signaling greatly aids information retention and can help reduce the cognitive load. Within the simulation, a set of carefully crafted instructions were delivered through a smartwatch displayed on the user's wrist, as depicted in Figure 7, allowing the operator to consult them at any time without interrupting the ongoing action. The instructions are available in two modes, toggled either by pressing a button on the controller or by directly tapping the watch. The first mode provides concise guidance to orient the user through the procedure, while the second offers more detailed instructions that describe each step with greater precision. A smartwatch was selected as the delivery interface because it is a familiar and intuitive device, enabling the user to access information at any moment without difficulty.

Figure 7 The VR smartwatch showing the short instruction summary (left) and its expanded version (right)

2.3 Testing session

The main objective of the test was to validate the benefits hypothesized during the design phase by testing whether the integration of VR could provide tangible advantages at different stages of a product's life cycle. Specifically, the effectiveness of the application was evaluated based on its ability to:

- Help designers in evaluating the practical effectiveness and feasibility of their project through the virtual world. Using VR, designers can experience a three-dimensional representation of the product even before its physical realization. This allows direct and intuitive analysis of aspects related to the arrangement of parts, accessibility, operator posture, and interaction with the surrounding environment. In this way, any accessibility issues can be identified and corrected in a time-saving manner, reducing costs associated with later modifications during prototyping or production.
- Improve maintenance by adding the possibility of visualize and perform specific procedures in an immersive manner without any risk. The virtual environment allows operators to follow step-by-step instructions from the technical manual while being able to visualize and simulate the actions to be performed directly on an interactive 3D model of the product. This approach allows operators to become familiar with complex or dangerous operations without exposing the user to real risks, or even in the absence of the physical product.

To accurately evaluate the usefulness and usability of the technology in the industrial context, a group of 9 expert designers was involved in the experimental activity. The decision to involve qualified professionals allowed for the collection of observations based on a real understanding of the design and production needs. Before the start of the test, a short introductory briefing was conducted with all participants, during which the purposes of the experience, how it would be carried out, and the main features of the virtual environments presented were explained. As depicted in Figure 8, the testing session was structured in three distinct stages:

STAGE 1 VR application	STAGE 2 Questionnaires	STAGE 3 Brainstorming session
Introduction & controls	Usability (SUS)	Strength & Weaknesses
Free roam	Perceived workload (NASA-TLX)	Opportunities & Threats
Maintenance procedure		Further developments

Figure 8 The three consecutive stages followed during the testing session

Stage 1: the functionalities of the VR-based application were shown, with the aim of providing participants with an overview of the main potential offered by virtual space. Two versions were developed from the same reference scenario. However, they differed from each other in the level of interactivity offered to the user. More specifically:

- the *Free roam* version featured limited interaction with the objects present in the scenario, but it offered greater freedom of movement within the virtual environment. The user could freely explore the facility, without restriction imposed by specific objectives or mandatory steps. Indeed, there were no tasks to be completed, as the main objective of this demo was to demonstrate the flexibility of the system and the possibility of easily implementing a maintenance procedure anywhere in the MORFEO environment.
- The *Maintenance procedure* version offered the opportunity to perform the procedure reported in **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** The user was guided through the procedure tasks by a sequence of step-by-step operating instructions. The application was designed for single user, with the aim of realistically simulating a maintenance operation and evaluating its effectiveness and usability within an immersive context.

Each participant had the opportunity to view all available versions and directly try out at least one of them. The testing setup is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Test session participants while trying the VR applications

Stage 2: Immediately after trying the VR applications, participants were asked to fill out questionnaires with the aim of collecting subjective evaluations of their experience concerning usability and perceived workload. Two validated scales were used: the System Usability Scale (SUS) [8], one of the most widely used and reliable standardized instruments in this field, was adopted for the assessment of usability. The scale consists of a questionnaire composed of ten items, to which the user responds according to a five-point Likert scale score. The result is a single value between 0 and 100, which provides a summary measure of the degree of perceived usability. To facilitate the interpretation of this score, the obtained values can be associated with qualitative descriptors (i.e., “poor,” “okay,” “excellent”) as proposed in [9] to better contextualize the outcomes. The second assessment tool used is the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) scale [10], a standard in literature to measure perceived workload while performing a task. The scale is based on six basic items, mental demand, physical demand, temporal demand, effort, performance, and frustration. These values are evaluated individually by the user. The collected scores can be combined to obtain an overall value, representative of the overall cognitive load perceived during the activity. Numerical scores were mapped to qualitative descriptors using quartiles established in existing literature [11]. This benchmarking allows individual scores to be accurately contextualized and compared against industry-standard performance tiers.

Stage 3: a brainstorming session was carried out, during which participants had the chance to highlight the potential and critical issues that had emerged in the use of the technology. This moment of open discussion facilitated the collection of qualitative observations and improvement proposals, offering a broader and more realistic view of the impact that VR-based tools could have in different areas of the product life cycle. Direct discussion among experts also made it possible to highlight strengths and possible limitations related to the adoption of the technology in concrete industrial contexts.

The activity was conducted on University premises, in a conference room, through a shared virtual whiteboard on the MIRO¹ platform. MIRO is collaborative software that allows multiple users to interact simultaneously on a shared digital board, facilitating the organization and sharing of ideas and opinions in real time. These medium enabled users to freely annotate observations, propose improvements, and discuss concerns that emerged during the test.

This session covered three main areas:

- Strengths and weaknesses of the application.
Here the focus was on identifying the main advantages and disadvantages of the application. The analysis focused on aspects such as the immersive experience, the quality of interaction, and the technical limitations experienced during use. This moment allowed the collection of direct impressions from users, highlighting both the potential of the system and areas where improvements are needed.
- Opportunities and threats that could arise for this type of application.
For this area, the discussion focused on the future potential offered by the application, exploring alternative use scenarios in industrial contexts in which the technology could be successfully implemented. Opportunities emerged related to staff training, collaborative validation of projects in development, remote support for complex operations, and reduction of costs and time associated with physical prototypes. This phase allowed the use of the system to be projected beyond the confines of the individual MORFEO demo, imagining its integration into the entire product life cycle
- Further development (i.e., extra feature that could help the technology arise in industry).
In the final phase of the brainstorming session, the focus shifted to identifying additional capabilities that could make the technology more attractive and easily adoptable on a large scale in the industrial setting. The suggestions that emerged included integration with existing business systems, such as PLM, the introduction of more intuitive and customizable interfaces, the use of artificial intelligence for integration support, and performance optimization for extended work sessions. These suggestions aim to bridge the gap between experimental prototyping and concrete implementation, accelerating the deployment of the technology in real manufacturing environments.

This subdivision was done to better organize the workflow and to better arrange ideas. This approach kept the discussion orderly and focused, while encouraging collaboration among participants and the categorization of contributions according to major themes. Each participant had the opportunity to interact directly with the board, modify it, and insert

¹ www.miro.com

proposals completely independently. To facilitate the organization and tracking of contributions, each user was assigned a specific colour so that the opinions and observations expressed by each person could be clearly distinguished.

3. RESULTS

The session has brought to light both advantages and disadvantages of the technology, also proposing solutions to the criticalities highlighted. A lot of expectations emerged towards the technology, especially towards possible future applications. The session highlighted both the advantages and disadvantages regarding the technology, while offering concrete suggestions to overcome the criticalities that emerged. The participants made several suggestions for improvement, demonstrating a positive attitude toward the application. In addition, many expectations have emerged regarding the evolutionary potential of the technology, with particular interest in its possible future applications in industry.

3.1 Questionnaire

The responses to the questionnaire were analysed to develop the indicators useful for assessing user experience. This process allowed raw data to be transformed into metrics useful for objectively interpreting the level of perceived usability and cognitive load experienced during interaction with the application.

Table 1 SUS and NASA-TLX scores

	SUS Score	NASA Weighted	Mental Demand	Physical Demand	Temporal Demand	Effort	Performance	Frustration
N	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Mean	81.9	35.6	31.1	23.3	26.1	20	73.1	15.2
Median	87.5	37.1	30	20	25	19	79	13
Std Dev	12.1	13.4	20.4	18.9	20.9	16.5	11.4	13.3
Min	65	17.8	5	0	0	0	48	0
Max	95	63.4	70	50	55	55	84	41

Taking into consideration the summary values obtained from the analysis of the responses, an average SUS scale value of 81,9 is observed, which indicates a "good" level of perceived usability of the application. As reported in [9], this value falls in the good category that reflects a general satisfaction on the part of users in using the system. However, when considering the median, 87,5, rather than the mean, this score falls between the "excellent" and "best imaginable" categories, suggesting that for most participants, interaction with the application was extremely smooth, intuitive, and free of difficulties.

Focusing on the NASA-TLX rates, a weighted mean value of 35.6 is observed, which denotes a low to moderate cognitive load, as suggested by [11]. Such a score is typical of tasks that require a minimum level of attention but are not particularly challenging or mentally fatiguing for the user. Among the six dimensions assessed, the low level of frustration is particularly notable, with a mean value of 15.2. Since this parameter is closely related to feelings of irritation, stress, and dissatisfaction, the data suggest that the system did not impose an excessive mental load and that the experience was manageable even for inexperienced users.

In general, the results from the questionnaire suggest that the experience was perceived as positive and non-fatiguing. In fact, most of the participants rated the interaction with the system as pleasant and free of elements of frustration or stress, confirming the effectiveness of the approach taken and the overall quality of the application. This feedback highlights how the virtual environment was able to provide an immersive experience without being cognitively taxing.

3.2 Brainstorming session results

During this session, the participants had the possibility to share their opinions about the VR application. This allowed qualitative feedback to be gathered in addition to the quantitative feedback provided by the validated questionnaires. The main strengths and opportunities that emerged during the discussion were:

- Knowledge sharing: the ability to remotely share operational or maintenance procedures is an important strength. This approach allows any concerns or critical issues to emerge that, without the presence of the actual product, might go unnoticed. Digital sharing also simplifies comparisons between different departments, even geographically distant ones, helping to improve communication between different work environments.
- Verification: with this visualization of the work environment, it was much easier to analyse the spaces, thus it can help with the verification of risks, accessibility, and estimating the time required to execute the various stages of the procedure. This approach makes it possible to identify any design or operational issues in advance, reducing the costs associated with late changes and improving the overall planning of interventions.
- Authoring: first-person visualization of maintenance operations provides the designer with a powerful tool to assist in defining and drafting the procedure. Living the experience directly enables documentation that is clearer and closer to actual operating conditions.

In addition to the strengths, some concerns related to the implementation of VR also emerged during the session. The comments collected focused mainly on two areas, which represent the main areas of attention to be considered for successful adoption of the technology. Those areas were:

- Time: implementing a detailed procedure within a virtual environment can be particularly time-consuming, especially if a high level of accuracy is the aim. In the absence of a dedicated operator with specific skills in modelling for a virtual environment or in the use of VR tools, the entire process can become complex to manage and results in a significant lengthening of development time.
- Usability: for short applications it might be inconvenient, as the complexity of implementation might outweigh any benefits; for large applications, on the other hand, there might be issues regarding the size of the models that would make the application more difficult to use on less powerful devices as, for example, standalone VR headset. These concerns relate to a more industrial approach to the technology and, if proven correct, could pose a problem for its scalability. However, the possible benefits that have been talked about should outweigh them, especially if the technology is implemented from the very start of the product life cycle. In fact, in response to these concerns, several recommendations emerged to counteract or limit possible problems, and then suggested an approach to facilitate their implementation, summarized in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Possible framework of implementation of VR design

In the final part of the session, attention was given to the possibility of creating a database, as this can help both future implementation and possible future replacements of procedure manuals, thus greatly reducing the time that designers employ to create maintenance procedures. Together with these suggestions, other fields of application for the technology have been proposed. These possible uses span through the life cycle of the product, thus making the implementation of VR more worthwhile. In particular, these proposals have been made:

- **Training people:** VR can be a particularly effective tool for training new personnel, especially in settings involving sensitive or fragile instrumentation, such as those found in laboratories. Through simulation, it is possible to replicate procedures realistically without running the risk of damaging expensive equipment or compromising safety.
- **Remote maintenance:** it could be particularly useful for remote control of robots operating in the real environment, allowing the operator to observe actions and surroundings in real time through a virtual interface. This approach can improve the accuracy and safety of operations by providing a complete and detailed view of the working environment without the need for a direct physical presence.
- **Connectivity:** through VR, teams distributed in different parts of the globe can collaborate more easily on the same project. This technology permits simultaneous sharing of virtual spaces and information, thus facilitating confrontation by overcoming geographical barriers.
- **Maintenance procedure verification:** an expert operator can be tracked through a motion capture suit during the actual execution of a maintenance procedure, thus allowing the correctness and effectiveness of the procedure to be accurately generated or verified.

4. LIMITATIONS AND NEXT STEPS

This work demonstrates the feasibility of using VR to support the design, validation, and training of maintenance procedures for complex astronomical instrumentation. The positive usability feedback and the low perceived workload suggest the potential advantages provided by this approach. However, several limitations currently constrain its effective adoption in an industrial context and must be addressed to enable broader and more systematic use.

A primary limitation is the time required to implement procedures and operations in the virtual environment, making the presence of a dedicated figure necessary, at least for the time being. This VR designer would oversee preparing and organizing the 3D models, adapting them appropriately to the specific requirements of the activities to be simulated. His/her role would be crucial in ensuring that the virtual experience would be functional and consistent to real operating conditions.

Closely related to this issue is the lack of an efficient and standardized pipeline for transforming 3D models from CAD design into virtual environments. Such a system would greatly simplify and speed up the integration process, reducing the workload required of the VR designer and shortening the overall development time, thus facilitating a more widespread and accessible use of VR in industrial settings.

Another critical limitation concerns the lack of standard coding to enable direct and efficient communication between CAD designers and VR designers. The introduction of a system of shared codes would allow the functions or nature of elements within the 3D model to be identified from the very beginning, greatly facilitating integration into the virtual environment. Such codes could, for example, be based on colour conventions or specific metadata assigned to elements during the CAD design phase. The ability to define and adopt these conventions would represent a major step forward in standardizing the process, reducing time and workload during the transition phase to VR.

From a technical perspective, the management of large and highly detailed models remains challenging, making it difficult, if not impractical, to run applications directly on standalone headset, especially when they have a high level of detail. One possible approach to overcome this limitation is to divide applications into simpler and lighter tasks that contain less information, so as to reduce the computational load.

In addition, the current implementation is limited to single-user interaction. While sufficient for initial validation and training, this restricts the potential for collaborative workflows. The integration of multi-user capabilities represents a key next step, opening new possibilities for collaboration among designers, technicians, and trainers. In such a context, one could envision direct interaction between those who design a procedure and those who will execute it, facilitating the exchange of observations and suggestions from the earliest stages. Similarly, the shared environment could be employed in training contexts, allowing multiple participants to observe or perform tasks in a coordinated manner, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of learning. This perspective suggests an evolution of the application toward increasingly collaborative and interactive scenarios, capable of leveraging diverse professional expertise and making virtual reality an even more integrated tool throughout the product life cycle.

To support Scalability and reuse, the creation of a shared database of tasks, easily accessible and browsable, is proposed. This database would have the dual benefit of simplifying the development of new applications encouraging the reuse of already implemented components, reducing time and work required for subsequent implementations. In particular, two-level architecture could be planned:

- A “blueprint database” intended for designers, containing generic and nonspecific tasks that could serve as a starting point for further customization.
- An “operational database”, accessible by maintainers or trainers, containing complete and ready-to-use tasks targeted toward training or operational use.

This distinction would allow information to be adjusted to the different professional profiles involved while guaranteeing scalability and ease of updating content over time.

Overall, while the current framework is not yet fully optimized for large-scale industrial deployment, it demonstrates a high level of maturity and clear practical value. The technology has proven effective in verifying accessibility and feasibility already during the design phase, enabling direct communication between maintenance procedure designers and end-users, thus reducing costs due to late-stage modifications. Future work should focus on reducing implementation complexity, improving interoperability between CAD and VR environments, and extending the system toward collaborative and scalable use cases. In this perspective, the possibility to extend the proposed approach and apply VR technologies to other ESO projects represents a key opportunity to encourage wider adoption across consortia, and potentially enhancing productivity and reducing implementation time.

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